

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

D6: Report on the spectral irradiance measurement intercomparison campaigns that were used to demonstrate the applicability of the newly developed transfer standards and methods in at least 3 end user spectroradiometric applications (solar radiation, actinic radiometry, lighting and photovoltaic) with total uncertainties as low as 1 % ($k = 2$)

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A3.2.6 Report on the measurement intercomparison for end-user applications

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1. Introduction

This report presents the results of the measurement intercomparison campaigns arranged as activities A3.2.1 – A.3.2.4. within the framework of the NEWSTAND project.

*A3.2.1 SFI Davos, supported by Aalto, GGO, CSIC, IS, ISFH, LNE, NPL, PTB and TUBITAK, will prepare a protocol and organise an intercomparison of the new transfer standards during a solar spectral irradiance measurement campaign in Davos. During the campaign, the new standard sources (at least 1 UV source (A1.2.1), at least 1 VIS source (A1.2.2), at least 1 NIR source (A1.2.3), at least 1 UV-VIS-NIR source (A1.2.4) and the 2 narrowband spectrally tuneable irradiance standard sources (A1.3.1, A1.3.2)) will be used to calibrate at least 5 of the participants' spectroradiometers which will be used to measure **solar spectral irradiance**. Moreover, at least 5 of the transfer standard spectroradiometers calibrated in A2.2.1-A2.2.7 will be used in the comparison as well.*

*A3.2.2 PTB, supported by GGO, RISE, Aalto, CSIC, IPQ, LNE, NPL, METAS, TUBITAK and VSL, will prepare a protocol and organise an intercomparison campaign to demonstrate the applicability of at least 1 of the newly developed transfer standards to the end user applications that involve **actinic radiometry and biological safety** measurements. Representative UV light sources from the end user applications will be measured using at least 3 of the participating spectroradiometers characterised in A2.2.1-A2.2.7 and calibrated using the standards (UV sources) developed in A1.2.1 and A1.2.4.*

*A3.2.3 PTB, supported by ISFH, SFI Davos, GGO, RISE, Aalto, CSIC, ISFH, LNE, NPL, VSL and IPQ, will prepare a protocol and organise an intercomparison campaign to demonstrate the applicability of at least 1 of the newly developed transfer standards to the end user applications involving **photovoltaic applications**. Representative light sources (simulating solar radiation) provided by the end users will be measured using at least 3 participating spectroradiometers, which were characterised in A2.2.1-A2.2.7, and calibrated using the standards developed in A1.2.1-A1.2.4, A1.3.1 and A1.3.2.*

*A3.2.4 PTB, supported by IS, GGO, RISE, Aalto, CSIC, CNAM, LNE, NPL, VSL and IPQ, will prepare a protocol and organise an intercomparison campaign to demonstrate the applicability, of at least 1 of the newly developed transfer standards, to the end user applications involving **lighting and colour measurements**. Representative light sources from the end users will be measured using at least 3 participating spectroradiometers, which were characterised in A2.2.1-A2.2.7, and calibrated using the standards developed in A1.2.2.*

1.1. Background and objectives

The main objective of the measurement intercomparison campaigns was to demonstrate applicability of the newly developed transfer standard sources to end user applications and to validate achievable transfer uncertainties by using array spectroradiometers that had been characterised and calibrated by the participating consortium partners representing National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and calibration laboratories. A good level of agreement between instruments demonstrates the applicability of the new sources and the suitability of the instruments as stable spectral irradiance standards.

For practical reasons, the intercomparison campaign to demonstrate the applicability to end-user applications that involve actinic radiometry, biological safety, photovoltaics, lighting and colour was arranged at PTB and the intercomparison campaign for solar spectral irradiance measurements was arranged at SFI Davos.

1.2. Scope of the intercomparisons

The scope of this intercomparison campaign encompasses the on-site measurement and evaluation of spectral irradiance $E(\lambda)$ across the ultraviolet (UV), visible (Vis), and near-infrared (NIR) spectral regions of several broadband sources for several economically relevant end-user applications. Each source is measured by characterized and calibrated array spectroradiometers provided by the participating partners.

2. Organisation of the intercomparison

The intercomparison of array spectroradiometer measurements for different applications was mainly carried out in the framework of a large-scale measurement intercomparison campaign organised at PTB during 20. - 24.10.2025. Dedicated measurement setups were prepared before the intercomparison allowing the entrance optics of the participating spectroradiometers to be easily installed for the measurements of pre-aligned sources at a given geometry in a reproducible way. To have a common reference data set, each source measured by the array spectroradiometers was also measured by a scanning double-monochromator spectroradiometer provided by PTB during the intercomparison. Moreover, as the intercomparison was carried out throughout several days period and each spectroradiometer was measuring each source at a different time, the stability of the spectral emissions of each source was monitored by a dedicated spectroradiometer that either was recording the signals continuously or did this before and after the measurements by each

participating spectroradiometer. After the campaign each participant processed own individual measurement results to yield spectral irradiances of the measured sources with the associated uncertainties and submitted them to PTB in an agreed data format. PTB as a pilot of the interlaboratory comparison analysed the provided results with the aim to determine agreement between the spectral irradiance measured by the participants and the reference data set.

The measurement campaign for solar spectral irradiance applications was carried out at SFI Davos during 23.-27.04.2026. Details of the measurement campaign are given in 8.1

3. Equipment and artifacts

During the intercomparisons at PTB, a scanning double-monochromator spectroradiometer, model SPECTRO320D, was as a reference instrument and three monitor spectroradiometers. Different array spectroradiometers brought by consortium partners were used to measure different light sources present at PTB.

Details of additional equipment of the measurement campaign in Davos are given in 8.2.1

3.1. Participating array spectroradiometers (detector-based standards)

The participating spectroradiometers represent a wide cross-section of current instrument architectures. They varied significantly in their core hardware, incorporating different detector technologies (such as back-thinned CCDs, CMOS, and InGaAs sensors), diverse optical input configurations, and varying spectral resolutions. The instruments had been characterised, calibrated and operated by the consortium partners during the measurements intercomparison campaign. Table 1 provides specific technical specifications of the measurement instruments utilized during the campaign.

Table 1 Technical specification of the participating array spectroradiometers.

Participant	Spectroradiometer Name	Label	Spectral Range / nm	No. of Pixels	Spectral Band-width / nm	Pixel spacing /nm/pixel	Entrance Optics diameter / mm
Aalto	CAS 140D	sp37	219 - 1029	1024x128	3.7	0.8	10
CSIC	Konica Minolta CS-1000	sp69	380 - 780	401	5	0.9	25
GGO	BTS2048-UV	sp79	200 - 430	2048	0.8	0.13	10
GGO	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp61	280 - 1050	2048	1	0.4	10
GGO	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp13	200 - 900	2048	2	0.34	10
GGO	BTS2048-NIR	sp43	950 - 1700	512	5.5	1.5	10
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	300 - 1100	1024x128	3.7	0.8	15
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	780 - 1700	512	5.7	2	15
NPL	SVC HR-1024i VNIR	sp76	340 - 1010	512	4	1.3	25
NPL	SVC HR-1024i SWIR	sp89	970 - 1910	256	13	2.18	25
PTB	BTS2048-UV	sp51	200 - 430	2048	0.8	0.13	10
PTB	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp23	280 - 1050	2048	1	0.4	10
PTB	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp49	200 - 900	2048	2	0.34	10
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS	sp08	200 - 830	1024x128	3	0.65	15
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR	sp77	300 -1100	1024x128	3.7	0.8	15

VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp47	190 - 1100	2048	1.88	0.46	10
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp35	190 - 1100	2048	2.44	0.46	10
PTB	Spectro320D	ref	190 - 1600	n/a	1 (2)		15

Unlike scanning double monochromator-based spectroradiometer, a number of array spectroradiometer properties such as stray light, bandpass and nonlinearity require mathematical corrections to achieve low measurement uncertainties. The participating institutes have independently characterized their instruments and applied the corrections to account for their properties such as nonlinearity, stray light, bandpass, and pixel-to-wavelength assignment. Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the specific characterizations and correction methodologies implemented by each participant before the campaign. The rigorousness of these corrections and the measurement evaluations is a critical factor, as it will directly influence the suitability of the instruments to be used as transfer standards.

For the spectral stray light correction within the spectral range of the instruments, stray light correction matrix (SCM) by Zong et al. [1] was applied by several partners as marked in Table 2. The stray light correction was also accompanied by long pass filter method for the out-of-range stray light in some cases. For the bandpass functions, some instruments were corrected by using the method by Woolliams et al [2]. A few participants corrected their instruments by using a simplified correction method based on an assumption of a triangular bandpass function. The nonlinearities of most instruments have been characterized and corrected by using polynomial functions applied to dark corrected signals.

Table 2 Overview of corrections applied by the participants of the comparison campaign to the participating array spectroradiometers.

Participant	Spectroradiometer Name	Label	Nonlinearity correction	Straylight correction	Bandpass correction	Pixel-wavelength assignment
Aalto	CAS 140D	sp37	no	no	No	manufacturer
CSIC	Konica Minolta CS-1000	sp69	no	no	no	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-UV	sp79	yes	SCM + OoR	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp61	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp13	yes	SCM + OoR	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-NIR	sp43	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	yes	no	No	manufacturer
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	yes	no	No	manufacturer
NPL	SVC HR-1024i VNIR	sp76	no	no	Triangular	Emission line method
NPL	SVC HR-1024i SWIR-1	sp89	no	no	Triangular	Emission line method
PTB	BTS2048-UV	sp51	yes	SCM + OoR	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line

PTB	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp23	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp49	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS	sp08	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR	sp77	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp47	yes	SCM	No	Emission line method
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp35	yes	SCM	No	Emission line method
PTB	Spectro320D	sp01	no	no	No	Emission line method

3.2. Monitor spectroradiometers

During the measurement campaign, following array spectroradiometers were used as the continuous monitoring instruments to verify the light sources stability and experimental integrity.

ms1: A Gigahertz-Optik BTS2048-UV-S-F spectroradiometer was deployed as a monitor spectroradiometer to track the stability of ultraviolet light sources throughout the measurements. The instrument is equipped with high sensitivity TE-cooled 2048-pixel back-thinned CCD detector and a BiTec sensor, operating over a spectral range of 200 nm to 430 nm. With an optical bandpass of about 0.8 nm and a pixel resolution of 0.13 nm/pixel, it provides accurate and stray-light corrected monitoring of the active light source.

ms2: A CAS140CT-151 spectroradiometer was employed as the monitor spectroradiometer to continuously monitor sources for the visible spectral range such as LIS-A² for any fluctuations or drift. The instrument covers a spectral range from 360 nm to 830 nm. It is equipped with 1024×128-pixel CCD detector, providing a spectral resolution (FWHM) of 2.2 nm and a data point interval of 0.5 nm.

ms3: A CAS-140CT UV-VIS optimized for UV-VIS spectral range (200 nm-830 nm) was used as a monitor spectroradiometer for sources such as SolSim. It is equipped with 1044×128-pixel TEC-cooled CCD detector, providing a spectral resolution (FWHM) of 2 nm and a data point interval of 0.6 nm. Due to its available spectral range, the array spectroradiometer is only partially suitable for monitoring the broadband sources in the NIR, but it can provide sufficient indication of the reproducibility of the irradiance levels.

3.3. The reference spectroradiometer

In this measurement intercomparison campaign, the Instrument Systems SPECTRO320D, a double monochromator-based system available at PTB was utilized as a reference spectroradiometer. As a double-monochromator spectroradiometer, it provides superior stray light suppression and features a symmetrical nearly triangular bandpass function that is constant throughout the spectral range. This combination of these properties serves as an excellent baseline for evaluating the performance of the participant array spectroradiometers measuring various sources with complex spectra.

The core specifications of used reference spectroradiometer are:

Optical design: Integration of a 320 mm focal length double monochromator with complete data acquisition and evaluation electronics.

Entrance optics and fibre bundle: EOP-146 transmissive diffusor with good cosine correction and medium throughput for the spectral range 190 nm – 2500 nm. OFG-465 mixed fibre bundle 5 m with a bundle diameter of 3 mm.

Spectral Range: Configurable from 190 nm (UV) to 1600 nm (IR) depending on the grating and detector combination. For this intercomparison, the reference spectroradiometer was operated in spectral range from 250 nm to 1600 nm.

UV-VIS range (190 nm to 885 nm): Measurements were performed using 1200 grooves/mm holographic or ruled grating paired with a high-sensitivity Photomultiplier Tube (PMT).

NIR range (885 nm to 1600 nm): The system was automatically switched to a 600 grooves/mm grating and a thermoelectrically cooled InGaAs detector.

Spectral Resolution: For the measurements the spectroradiometer was configured to use 1 nm FWHM bandpass in the UV-VIS range and 2 nm in the NIR range. The spectral scans of the sources were carried out with a sampling interval of 1 nm.

Data acquisition: The recording and evaluation of measurement data using the SpecWin Pro software which provides full control over the SPECTRO 320D hardware.

Calibration: To ensure the absolute accuracy of the reference measurements, the spectroradiometer's spectral irradiance responsivity calibrations were carried out against secondary spectral irradiance standards via measuring a 250 W halogen lamp and a 30 W deuterium lamp at a calibration distance of 300 mm.

Due to the transmission characteristics of the input optics, particularly in measurements below 300 nm, relatively high standard deviations were observed. This resulted in higher measurement uncertainties in some cases, as well as higher noise of deviations in comparison measurements.

4. Measurement protocol and conditions

Dedicated measurement setups were prepared at PTB with different sources in UV-VIS-NIR spectral ranges. These setups enabled the rapid and highly reproducible positioning of each participant's entrance optics relative to the pre-aligned light sources, guaranteeing a consistent measurement geometry across all evaluations. All the sources were precisely mounted and aligned relative to the spectroradiometer's entrance optics. Each source was positioned at a specific measurement distance: KSL102, KSL103, and KSL104 were set at 700 mm, 449 mm, and 300 mm, respectively. The SolSim source was placed at 787 mm while the LIS-A2 was kept at a distance of 450 mm. The light sources were operated and measured one after another. The individual measurement setups were optically isolated from one another using black absorbing walls to preventing background radiation from neighbouring light sources. Once a source was stabilized, the participants within the designated group installed their instruments one after another to record the data. All the spectroradiometer's measurements were accompanied by monitor spectroradiometer measurements to ensure the stability of sources. Apart from this, there was a separate optical set up utilizing the pen-ray lamps to verify the wavelength scale of the arrays spectroradiometers.

Following measurement procedure was used for spectroradiometer's measurements:

1. The entrance optics of the participating spectroradiometer was carefully aligned directly in front of the active light source at the specified measurement distances.
2. The measurement parameters were verified, and an optimal integration time and number of averages was set for the measurements.
3. A sequence of repeated measurements of the light source was executed and recorded.
4. Measurement was taken to quantify the ambient room stray light being scattered into the detector by placing a shader in the optical beam.
5. Additional dark measurements with the internal shutter of spectroradiometer were performed, if required.

In the end, out-of-range measurements were conducted using an OoR-filter (830 nm long-pass filter) by certain spectroradiometers that needed the respective corrections.

5. Actinic radiometry and biological safety measurement applications

In actinic radiometry and photobiological safety, the spectral irradiance of light sources is measured in the wavelength range of 200–400 nm (actinic UV) as well as in the visible and infrared regions to quantify photochemical and thermal biological effects on skin and eyes. The spectral irradiance is measured using a spectroradiometer and weighted with biological action spectra such as the erythral action spectrum for skin reddening and the UV hazard action spectrum for general UV-induced biological damage. Further hazards such as corneal damage, retinal damage from blue light (300–700 nm), premature skin aging from UV-A, and thermal burns can also be assessed. The measured values are compared with the limit values of the ICNIRP

to classify the photobiological risk of lamps, LEDs, and other light sources, thereby ensuring occupational safety and product safety.

5.1. Measured sources

5.1.1. XWS30 laser-induced xenon plasma source transfer standard

Figure 1 XWS30 laser-induced xenon plasma source.

The ISTEQ XWS-30 is a commercially available, table-top laser-induced Xenon plasma light source designed to generate a high-radiance, point-like plasma spot that emits broadband optical radiation spanning from the ultraviolet (UV) through the visible (VIS) to the near-infrared (NIR) spectrum. In the context of this study, the device is adapted to serve as a transfer standard for spectral irradiance calibration. To transform the raw point source into a usable calibration standard, the system is equipped with off-the-shelf optics: a fused silica plano-convex lens collimates the radiation to minimize divergence, while a pair of crossed cylindrical microlens arrays (MLA) homogenizes the beam to produce a spatially uniform, flat-top irradiance field at a working distance of 300 mm. This specific configuration significantly enhances spatial uniformity, achieving measurement deviations of less than 0.1% for spectroradiometer entrance optics with diameters ranging from 10 mm to 30 mm.

Regarding performance, the adapted source demonstrates excellent temporal stability and reproducibility within $\pm 0.5\%$ across the VIS to NIR spectral ranges after a warm-up period of approximately 15 to 20 minutes. However, the system faces specific challenges related to its emission profile, particularly strong xenon spectral peaks and ozone absorption features around 254 nm caused by ultraviolet-C radiation. The adapted XWS-30 provides lower irradiance than traditional halogen standards in the visible and near-infrared regions, it maintains higher irradiance levels in the ultraviolet range.

Figure 2 Spectral irradiance of XWS30 measured at 300 mm distance by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

5.1.2. Aalto-UV transfer standard UV-LED source

The Aalto-UV is a broadband ultraviolet light source developed by Aalto University, specifically designed for the wavelength region between 250 nm and 450 nm. Its architecture combines a UVC LED matrix emitting at 277 nm with a UVA and UVB phosphor disk; the phosphor absorbs a portion of the LED radiation and re-emits it at longer wavelengths to cover the UV-A and UV-B spectral regions. The optical design incorporates a UV-coated 75 mm plano-convex lens to collect and direct the intensity, with the reference plane for measurements defined as the outermost surface of the protective cap, establishing a standard measurement distance of 500 mm.

While the source demonstrates good stability after a recommended one-hour warm-up period, it exhibits a gradual intensity decay over time, dropping by 0.03% per hour in the LED peak region (250–295 nm) and by 0.11% per hour in the phosphor region (296–450 nm). The spectral output is characterized by a primary excitation peak at 277 nm, accompanied by secondary peaks and a long-wavelength tail from the phosphor, delivering spectral irradiance levels comparable to a 1000 W tungsten halogen lamp at 500 mm distance. During the interlaboratory comparison, the Aalto-UV proved to be highly stable, showing minimal wavelength-dependent variations and an average deviation of only 0.18% between the first two days of measurement, with a slight increase of 0.89% on the third day attributed to potential environmental factors rather than source degradation. Although spatial uniformity is somewhat limited by the lens design, the source serves effectively as a transfer standard, provided that measurement instruments are carefully characterized to handle the steep spectral slopes and that corrections are applied for the gradual intensity decay.

Figure 3 Spectral irradiance of Aalto-UV measured at 500 mm distance by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 450 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

5.1.3. CALIS-UV transfer standard UV-LED source

Figure 4 UV-LED Source CALIS-UV.

The CALIS-UV is a broadband ultraviolet light source developed by TÜBITAK, engineered to cover the wavelength range from 250 nm to 405 nm with an irradiance exceeding 1 mW/m² at each wavelength. The core of the system consists of 79 individual UV LEDs arranged in fourteen distinct spectral groups on a circular printed circuit board (PCB) to ensure uniform irradiation. To manage the significant thermal load generated by this high density of LEDs, the PCB is mounted on a custom-made thermoelectric cooler (TEC) that maintains the board at a target temperature of 25 °C by fixing the TEC cold plate at 18 °C. The system is driven by a multi-channel current controller, allowing for flexible adjustment of the spectral power distribution by setting individual currents for each of the 14 LED groups, all managed via dedicated software.

The source produces a spectrum characterized by multiple low-intensity peaks between 260 nm and 350 nm, alongside two dominant emission bands near 365 nm and 395 nm, where the maximum peak irradiance reaches approximately 0.27 W·m⁻²·nm⁻¹. The source demonstrates excellent temporal stability after a one-hour warm-up period; variations remain within ±1% in the 250–300 nm range and improve to below ±0.5% in the 300 nm – 405 nm range once thermal and electrical equilibrium is reached. During the interlaboratory comparisons, the CALIS-UV proved highly stable above 325 nm, with day-to-day deviations of roughly 0.4%, though some instability was noted below 325 nm due to current fluctuations in the short-wavelength LEDs. While the spatial homogeneity is not as ideal as a point source due to the distributed nature of the LEDs, it achieves a uniformity of 1.2% over a 6 cm by 7 cm area at the standard 500 mm measurement distance. The source delivers spectral irradiance levels that exceed those of a 1000 W tungsten halogen lamp at the same distance, particularly in the UV-A range, making it a robust candidate for transfer standard applications provided that instruments are capable of resolving its narrow spectral peaks.

Figure 5 Spectral irradiance of CALIS-UV measured at 500 mm distance by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

5.1.4. UV-INSPECTOR150

The Helling UV Inspector 150 is a rugged, handheld inspection lamp designed for non-destructive testing (NDT) and fluorescence applications, featuring an IP65 rating for dust and water resistance. It combines three high-power 365 nm UV-LEDs (with a narrow half-width of approximately 10 nm) in a single aluminium housing, allowing for versatile inspection under UV radiation. The device is powered by a standard 230 V AC mains supply with a 5-meter detachable cable, consuming approximately 15 watts, and offers a pre-adjustable UV intensity ranging from 3,000 to 10,000 μW/cm² measured at a distance of 400 mm. Designed for durability and longevity, the LEDs have an operational life of approximately 10,000 hours.

Figure 6 Spectral irradiance of Aalto-UV measured by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

5.2. Spectroradiometer measurements

The measurements were focused on the UV spectral range in order to calculate the relevant actinic quantities in the ultraviolet region. For this purpose, a wavelength range of approximately 250 to 450 nm was considered for the different sources, and some of the UV sources showed no irradiance outside this range.

The spectral measurements for the XWS30 showed a comparatively good agreement with the reference spectrum, with sp79 deviating slightly toward lower irradiance values (Figure 7). A similar pattern was observed for the Aalto-UV source, although more pronounced deviations appeared at the spectral edges, while still remaining within the combined measurement uncertainties (Figure 8). For the CALIS-UV source, the deviations at the flanks were somewhat larger, especially around 360 nm, with sp79 again measuring slightly lower irradiance than the reference and sp51 showing stronger positive deviations (Figure 9). The UV INSPECTOR150, being a very narrowband source, revealed clear differences between the individual spectrometers, some of which exceeded the combined measurement uncertainty (Figure 10).

Figure 7 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the XWS30 source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 8 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the Aalto-UV source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 9 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the CALIS-UV source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 10 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the UV-INSPECTOR150 source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.3. Comparison of radiometric quantities

The measurements for actinic radiometry and photobiological safety covered UVC, UVB, and UVA irradiance, as well as the erythemal (E_{ery}) and UV hazard (E_{uvh}) irradiance (Table 3). The comparison showed only small deviations for many devices measuring the different sources (Table 4 - Table 7), but some spectroradiometers differed more noticeably depending on the wavelength region and the action spectrum used. In particular, deviations in the UVC range had a much stronger impact on the erythemal and UV hazard irradiance, since weighting amplifies spectral differences. The sp79 generally measured slightly too low, while the sp51 showed higher irradiance values in the Kalis UV comparison. For the UV Inspector, not only UVA, effective, and UV hazard irradiance were evaluated, but also the center wavelength and full width at half maximum of the LED peak, with generally good agreement despite stronger differences at the spectral flanks. Overall, the results show that photobiologically weighted measurements are highly sensitive to spectral shape changes, especially in the UVC range, where stray-light-related calibration issues can become visible.

Table 3 Irradiance in UVA, UVB and UVC, for erythemal hazard and with respect to UV-hazard for the different sources calculated from the spectral irradiance measurements of the reference spectroradiometer.

	E(UVC)	E(UVB),	E(UVA)	E _{ery}	E _{uvh}
XWS30	0.2979 W/m ²	0.9810 W/m ²	0.3597 W/m ²	0.2589 W/m ²	0.2979 W/m ²
Aalto-UV	0.02583 W/m ²	0.1047 W/m ²	0.3761 W/m ²	0.06789 W/m ²	0.04934 W/m ²
CALIS-UV	0.24077 W/m ²	0.2794 W/m ²	3.449 W/m ²	0.3616 W/m ²	0.2679 W/m ²
UV-INSPECTOR150		8.502608 W/m ²	0.00336 W/m ²	0.000878 W/m ²	8.502608 W/m ²

Table 4 Deviation of radiometric quantities calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the XWS30 source.

Spectrometer	E(UVC)	E(UVB),	E(UVA)	E _{ery}	E _{uvh}
sp08	0.4 %	0.4 %	0.6 %	0.4 %	2.3 %
sp13	-0.7 %	-0.5 %	-0.5 %	-0.7 %	1.2 %
sp49	-6.3 %	-3.1 %	-0.6 %	-5.1 %	-3.5 %
sp51	-1.1 %	0.1 %	0.0 %	-0.4 %	1.4 %
sp79	-1.8 %	-2.0 %	-2.3 %	-1.9 %	0.0 %

Table 5 Deviation of radiometric quantities calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the Aalto-UV source.

Spectrometer	E(UVC)	E(UVB),	E(UVA)	E _{ery}	E _{uvh}
sp08	1.3 %	0.7 %	0.8 %	0.4 %	0.5 %
sp13	0.5 %	1.3 %	1.1 %	1.2 %	1.3 %
sp49	-4.7 %	-2.1 %	-0.4 %	-3.4 %	-3.7 %
sp51	-1.6 %	-0.1 %	0.4 %	-0.4 %	-0.5 %
sp79	-2.0 %	-2.3 %	-2.3 %	-2.2 %	-2.2 %

Table 6 Deviation of radiometric quantities calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the CALIS-UV source.

Spectrometer	E(UVC)	E(UVB),	E(UVA)	E _{ery}	E _{uvh}
sp08	1.4 %	3.0 %	1.8 %	1.8 %	1.4 %
sp13	1.3 %	0.6 %	-0.8 %	0.8 %	1.1 %
sp49	-5.4 %	-2.5 %	-1.9 %	-4.8 %	-4.6 %
sp51	2.5 %	3.5 %	1.9 %	2.8 %	2.6 %
sp79	-0.5 %	-1.3 %	-2.5 %	-0.8 %	-0.8 %

Table 7 Deviation of radiometric quantities and differences of centroid wavelength (367.4 nm) and FWHM (8.98 nm) calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the UV-INSPECTOR150 source.

Spectrometer	E(UVA)	E _{ery}	E _{uvh}	$\lambda_{centroid}$	FWHM
sp08	3.5 %	3.0 %	3.0 %	0.3 nm	0.18 nm
sp13	2.8 %	2.2 %	2.2 %	0.2 nm	0.16 nm

sp37	-1.5 %	-1.1 %	-1.1 %	0.2 nm	0.67 nm
sp49	1.2 %	0.6 %	0.6 %	0.2 nm	-0.13 nm
sp51	3.3 %	3.5 %	3.5 %	-0.2 nm	-0.26 nm
sp79	-0.9 %	-0.7 %	-0.7 %	-0.1 nm	-0.21 nm

6. Photovoltaic applications

In the field of photovoltaics, spectral measurements are essential for characterizing solar simulators. These simulators can then be used to test and calibrate solar modules or reference solar cells, ensuring reliable performance under standardized conditions.

The IEC 60904-9:2020 standard specifies in detail the spectral ranges—known as bins—in which irradiance shares must lie, ensuring that each bin delivers a proportionally equal amount of irradiance (Table 8). Additionally, the AM1.5 spectral coverage (SPC) and AM1.5 spectral deviations can be evaluated, as modern LED-based simulators can achieve good bin conformity but may introduce subtle deviations that lead to measurement errors during testing.

During the intercomparison, spectral measurements were performed on two solar simulators: the high-end Sinus 3000 and a cost-effective Oriel model marketed as a low-cost variant (SolSim). The comparison of various spectroradiometers was carried out via bin calculations relative to a reference instrument, quantifying deviations in the spectral distribution to ensure the reliability of calibrations in PV production.

Table 8 Global reference solar spectral irradiance distribution given in IEC 60904-3 contribution of wavelength intervals to total irradiance in the extended wavelength range 300 nm to 1200 nm.

	Wavelength range	Percentage of total irradiance in the wavelength range 300 nm to 1 200 nm	Cumulative integrated irradiance
	nm	%	%
1	300 to 470	16,61	16,61
2	470 to 561	16,74	33,35
3	561 to 657	16,67	50,02
4	657 to 772	16,63	66,65
5	772 to 919	16,66	83,31
6	919 to 1 200	16,69	100,00

6.1. Measured sources

6.1.1. SINUS3000 LED solar simulator

Figure 11 Solar Simulator SINUS3000 with six activated LED Panels.

The SINUS-3000 ADVANCED at PTB (Figure 11) is a continuous LED-based solar simulator from WVELABS, operational since late 2024 in working group 4.53 "Solarmodule" for high-precision calibration of photovoltaic modules under standard test conditions (STC). It employs 25 individually adjustable LED types covering a wavelength range from 330–1200 nm to accurately replicate the AM1.5G spectrum with exceptional homogeneity, rating A+A+A+ after IEC60904-3 (Figure 12). It enables measurements of I-V curves, open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short-circuit current (I_{sc}), maximum power point (P_{mpp}), and spectral responsivity of solar modules. Equipped with a temperature chamber, it supports irradiation and temperature-dependent tests per IEC 61853-1, achieving a world-leading expanded measurement uncertainty of 0.9% for crystalline silicon module power output – the lowest globally reported. Long-term stability is outstanding, with an annual standard deviation of the P_{mpp} of a reference module of less than 0.2%. It is an ideal system for large-format modules and emerging technologies like perovskite-Si tandems through flexible spectral control of top and bottom cells for extended exposures without degradation.

Figure 12 Spectral irradiance of the SINUS3000 solar simulator measured by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

6.1.2. SoISim low-cost solar simulator

Figure 13 Solar Simulator LS0306 "SoISim".

The LOT Low-Cost Solar Simulator LS0306 is a compact xenon short-arc solar simulator designed for small-area testing of photovoltaic and photosensitive materials (Figure 13). It uses a 300 W ozone-free xenon lamp integrated into a self-contained housing, providing a collimated beam with an illuminated field diameter of about 40 mm at a working distance of 180 mm. The system typically delivers at least one sun ($\geq 100 \text{ mW/cm}^2$) over this area, with spectral matching to AM1.5G (ASTM 927-91 / IEC 60904-9 Class A in UV/VIS) thanks to integrated AM filters and a 90° beam turner mirror (Figure 14). The simulator is intended as a low-cost laboratory solution for I-V characterization of organic PV, dye-sensitized cells, and similar small devices, and

can be combined with reference Si cells and shutters for calibrated steady-state or chopped-light measurements.

Figure 14 Spectral irradiance of SolSim measured by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

6.1.3. LDLS-EQ99 laser driven light source

The Energetiq EQ-99X is a commercially available, fiber-coupled laser-induced plasma light source that generates a high-radiance xenon plasma spot, emitting broadband optical radiation from the ultraviolet (UV) through the visible (VIS) to the near-infrared (NIR) spectrum. It is adapted in this study to function as a transfer standard for spectral irradiance. The adaptation involves a specific optical assembly consisting of a fused-silica aspheric plano-convex lens with a 60 mm focal length to collimate the plasma emission, followed by a UV-grade 600-grit ground glass diffuser to homogenize the beam. This configuration produces a weakly diverging, spatially uniform irradiance field with a maximum diameter of approximately 15 mm. The LDLS-EQ-99 setup incorporates a dedicated, temperature-controlled monitor detector that samples a fraction of the beam via a beam-splitting window, allowing for real-time correction of temporal drifts during measurements (Figure 15).

In terms of performance, the EQ-99X exhibits temporal stability within $\pm 0.5\%$ when corrected using the monitor detector, although it displays inherent long-term drifts ranging from 0.1% to 0.5% per hour and short-term fluctuations exceeding 0.5% within minutes. Spatially, the homogenization reduces peak-to-peak illumination variation to 19% over a 9 mm by 9 mm area at an 18 cm working distance, though this uniformity degrades to 37% at a standard 50 cm working distance. A distinct limitation of this specific adaptation is the presence of a borosilicate crown glass window on the source housing, which blocks all optical output below approximately 350 nm, rendering it unsuitable for deep UV calibration (Figure 16). Furthermore, the combination of collimation and diffuser optics reduces the overall spectral irradiance compared to traditional halogen lamps across the measured VIS and NIR ranges. Despite these challenges regarding stability, uniformity at longer distances, and UV cutoff, the system demonstrates the potential to serve as a broadband transfer standard when its specific drift characteristics are actively compensated for via the integrated monitor detector.

Figure 15 Laser driven light source LDLS-EQ99.

Figure 16 Spectral irradiance of LDLS-EQ-99 measured by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

6.2. Spectroradiometer measurements

Figure 17 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the SINUS300 source by several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 18 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the SolSim source by several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 19 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the LDLS-EQ99 source by several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

6.3. Comparison of radiometric quantities

The integrals over the wavelength intervals of the individual bins were calculated from the measured spectra in accordance with IEC 60904-3 and compared with the values derived from the reference spectrum (Table 9, Table 11 and Table 13). The deviations are listed in Table 10, Table 12 and Table 14.

Table 9 Measured irradiances in wavelength intervals given in IEC 60904-3 and percentage of total irradiance for the SINUS3000 solar simulator.

Reference spectroradiometer	1 300 nm - 470 nm	2 470 nm - 561 nm	3 561 nm - 657nm	4 657 nm - 772 nm	5 772 nm - 919 nm	6 919 nm - 1200 nm	300 nm - 1200 nm
irradiance	15.60 W/m ²	15.12 W/m ²	13.98 W/m ²	14.55 W/m ²	12.31 W/m ²	14.10 W/m ²	85.65 W/m ²
Percentage	18,21 %	17,65 %	16.33 %	16.98 %	14.37 %	16,46 %	100 %

Table 10 Deviation of irradiances calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the SINUS3000 solar simulator.

Spectrometer	1 300 nm - 470 nm	2 470 nm - 561 nm	3 561 nm - 657nm	4 657 nm - 772 nm	5 772 nm - 919 nm	6 919 nm - 1200 nm	300 nm - 1200 nm
sp23	-0.6 %	-0.3 %	-0.1 %	-0.1 %	2.1 %	4.4 %	0.5 %
sp35	-6.7 %	-4.6 %	0.4 %	1.7 %	1.6 %	2.0 %	-1.2 %
sp37	-1.7 %	-1.4 %	-1.8 %	-2.0 %	-0.1 %	2.9 %	-1.1 %
sp38	-1.6 %	-1.1 %	-0.7 %	-0.8 %	0.9 %	3.2 %	-0.1 %
sp47	-4.6 %	-3.5 %	2.4 %	1.7 %	1.0 %	1.6 %	-0.4 %
sp61	-1.3 %	-0.2 %	-0.1 %	-0.2 %	1.5 %	1.0 %	-0.0 %
sp76	-5.7 %	-0.3 %	0.6 %	1.0 %	3.9 %	17.8 %	0.7 %
sp77	-0.7 %	-0.9 %	-0.5 %	-0.5 %	1.1 %	1.9 %	-0.0 %

Table 11 Measured irradiances in wavelength intervals given in IEC 60904-3 and percentage of total irradiance for the SolSim solar simulator.

Reference spectroradiometer	1 300 nm - 470 nm	2 470 nm – 561 nm	3 561 nm – 657nm	4 657 nm – 772 nm	5 772 nm – 919 nm	6 919 nm – 1200 nm	300 nm – 1200 nm
irradiance	10.15 W/m ²	11.85 W/m ²	11.51 W/m ²	11.51 W/m ²	12.53 W/m ²	10.94 W/m ²	68.51 W/m ²
Percentage	14,82 %	17,30 %	16.80 %	16.81 %	18.30 %	10,91 %	100 %

Table 12 Deviation of irradiances calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the SolSim solar simulator.

Spectrometer	1 300 nm - 470 nm	2 470 nm – 561 nm	3 561 nm – 657nm	4 657 nm – 772 nm	5 772 nm – 919 nm	6 919 nm – 1200 nm	300 nm – 1200 nm
sp23	-1.2 %	-0.8 %	-0.7 %	-0.6 %	-0.9 %	-1.2 %	-0.9 %
sp35	-8.1 %	-4.1 %	0.3 %	0.6 %	-3.2 %	1.6 %	-2.2 %
sp38	-1.9 %	-1.7 %	-1.4 %	-1.3 %	-1.8 %	-0.6 %	-1.4 %
sp47	-6.1 %	-2.9 %	2.0 %	-0.0 %	-3.6 %	-0.6 %	-1.9 %
sp61	-1.6 %	-0.9 %	-0.7 %	-0.8 %	-1.6 %	0.1 %	-1.0 %
sp76	-3.9 %	1.1 %	1.2 %	1.9 %	2.2 %	10.1 %	1.4 %
sp77	-0.5 %	-0.4 %	-0.5 %	-0.4 %	-0.4 %	0.4 %	-0.3 %

Table 13 Measured irradiances in wavelength intervals given in IEC 60904-3 and percentage of total irradiance for the LDLS-EQ99 transfer standard.

Reference spectroradiometer	1 300 nm - 470 nm	2 470 nm – 561 nm	3 561 nm – 657nm	4 657 nm – 772 nm	5 772 nm – 919 nm	6 919 nm – 1200 nm	300 nm – 1200 nm
irradiance	1.13 W/m ²	1.01 W/m ²	1.09 W/m ²	1.35 W/m ²	3.8 W/m ²	5.11 W/m ²	13.49 W/m ²
Percentage	8.39 %	7,48 %	8.07 %	9.99 %	28.19 %	37,87 %	100 %

Table 14 Deviation of irradiances calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the LDLS-EQ99 transfer standard.

Spectrometer	1 300 nm - 470 nm	2 470 nm – 561 nm	3 561 nm – 657nm	4 657 nm – 772 nm	5 772 nm – 919 nm	6 919 nm – 1200 nm	300 nm – 1200 nm
sp23	0.3 %	1.1 %	1.8 %	2.7 %	4.2 %	3.9 %	3.1 %
sp35	-5.0 %	-2.2 %	2.1 %	2.0 %	-1.0 %	-3.9 %	-1.9 %
sp38	-1.3 %	-0.7 %	-0.5 %	-0.1 %	1.2 %	1.5 %	0.7 %
sp47	-3.5 %	-2.5 %	2.6 %	1.2 %	-1.1 %	0.8 %	-0.2 %
sp61	-0.9 %	1.2 %	1.8 %	2.5 %	3.7 %	2.7 %	2.4 %
sp76	-16.6 %	-12.8 %	-13.7 %	-14.6 %	-16.3 %	-10.9 %	-14.0 %

7. Lighting and colour measurement applications

Photometry and colorimetry characterize lamps using human-perceived light quantities and color properties that are calculated from spectral irradiance. Photometric quantities include luminous flux (lumen, lm), illuminance (lux, lx), luminous intensity (candela, cd), and luminance (cd/m²). They can be derived by weighting the spectral irradiance with the human eye's luminous efficiency function $V(\lambda)$ for photopic vision and multiplying by the maximum luminous efficacy $K_m = 683 \text{ lm/W}$. Colorimetric quantities describe the chromaticity of light sources and include CIE color coordinates (x, y, z), correlated color temperature (CCT in Kelvin), dominant wavelength, color rendering index (CRI/Ra), and color purity. These parameters are computed by integrating the spectral irradiance spectrum with the CIE color matching functions ($\bar{x}(\lambda)$, $\bar{y}(\lambda)$, $\bar{z}(\lambda)$) to obtain tristimulus values (X, Y, Z), from which all color coordinates and derived metrics follow. Goniospectroradiometers enable simultaneous determination of all relevant photometric values, color coordinates, dominant wavelength, and color temperature from a single spectral measurement, providing comprehensive characterization of LED lamps, traditional light sources, and lighting systems for quality control and compliance with lighting standards.

7.1. Measured sources

7.1.1. RGB LED light source

Figure 20 LED-based light source RGB.

The RGB LED light source consists of a matrix of high-power LEDs and is thermoelectrically stabilized to maintain a controlled operating temperature and ensure consistent spectral output. The compact, actively cooled design supports stable optical performance during measurements and makes the source suitable for spectroradiometric characterization and calibration tasks.

Figure 21 Spectral irradiance of RGB measured at 450 mm distance by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

7.1.2. NICHIA transfer standard light source

Figure 22 LED-based light source NICHIA.

The Nichia NLSW30S01D is a LED standard lamp designed for photometric and radiometric applications, serving as a stable reference source for calibrating measurement instruments. The device features a high-quality white LED chip (typically based on Nichia's nitride technology with a phosphor conversion) housed in a robust, thermally optimized package to ensure minimal spectral and intensity drift during operation. It is engineered to provide a consistent and reproducible spectral power distribution (SPD) and luminous intensity, making it suitable as a transfer standard or reference illuminant in metrology laboratories. The unit is designed for DC operations with precise current control to maintain thermal equilibrium, which is critical for preserving output stability over time.

Figure 23 Spectral irradiance of NICHIA measured at 450 mm distance by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 700 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

7.1.3. LIS-A LED-based light source

Figure 24 LED-based Source LIS-A.

The Luminous Intensity Standard – Type A (LIS-A) is a highly stable, LED-based calibration light source developed within the EURAMET project "Future photometry based on solid-state lighting products" (16SIB03) and commercialized to serve as a modern alternative to traditional incandescent standard lamps like the W41/G. It is designed specifically for lighting and testing laboratories to calibrate photometers with a spectral power distribution that closely matches modern solid-state lighting (SSL) products. The device operates stably within a current range between 10 mA and 150 mA, with a recommended operating current of 100 mA to achieve an optimal balance of high stability, low aging effects, and sufficient light output. Due to its robust

solid-state construction, the source experiences significantly less degradation than older tungsten-based standards, losing 10 to 100 times less intensity over time, making it exceptionally reliable for inter-laboratory comparisons and transportation. By integrating precise thermal management and spectral control, the LIS-A ensures the metrological stability required to support the transition from thermal to solid-state lighting standards in national metrology institutes.

Figure 25 Spectral irradiance of LIS-A measured at 450 mm distance by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 450 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

7.1.4. LIS-A² transfer standard light source

Figure 26 LED-based transfer standard LIS-A².

The LIS-A² is a broadband transfer standard light source developed for the visible spectral range (360 nm to 830 nm) within the NEWSTAND project. Its architecture builds upon the earlier LIS-A design but features a hybrid LED configuration to achieve a spectrum that closely approximates the ideal CIE Illuminant E (equal energy). The source comprises a circular array of ten broadband, phosphor-converted Yujiled LEDs arranged in an outer ring to provide a smooth, continuous output across the visible spectrum, supplemented by five specific UV LEDs (with peak wavelengths at 365, 375, 385, 395, and 405 nm) mounted in the center to ensure sufficient irradiance in the short-wavelength region.

To ensure metrological stability, the LEDs are mounted on a temperature-stabilized heatsink and driven by three independent current circuits (two for the broadband LEDs and one for the UV LEDs) using high-precision Source Meters, maintaining a stable thermal equilibrium. The LIS-A² offers significant advantages over halogen standards, including negligible infrared emission (which eliminates stray light issues in the blue region), superior long-term stability with minimal aging drift, and a spectral distribution that better represents real-world lighting conditions. However, it requires a more complex setup involving temperature controllers and multiple power supplies compared to simple incandescent lamps.

Figure 27 Spectral irradiance of LIS-A² measured at 450 mm distance by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 450 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

7.2. Spectroradiometer measurements

For the determination of photometric and colorimetric quantities, a spectral range of about 350 to 900 nm was used, depending on the source. The spectral results agreed largely within the combined measurement uncertainties with the reference spectrum, although for the RGB source some devices showed somewhat larger deviations at weak signals, for example around 600 nm, where the uncertainties were also higher. For the NICHIA source, and especially for LIS-A and LIS-A², more pronounced deviations were observed at the sharp LED edges, most clearly for LIS-A² with sp69 and sp76. This can be explained by incomplete bandpass correction in the measurement results and the large spectral bandwidth of these spectroradiometers compared to the spectral features of the LED sources.

Figure 28 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the RGB source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 29 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the NICHIA source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 30 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the LIS-A source by several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 31 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the LIS-A2 source by several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

7.3. Comparison of photometric and colorimetric quantities

For the photometric and colorimetric measurements, illuminance, CIE xyz normalized chromaticity coordinates, and correlated color temperature (CCT) were determined as far as available (Table 15, CCT not applicable for RGB source). The RGB source exhibited somewhat larger deviations between the instruments in illuminance, partly because it turned out not to be very stable during the measurement campaign and the results had to be corrected for other measurement days (Table 16). For the Nichia source (Table 17) as well as for LIS-A (Table 18) and LIS-A² (Table 19), the deviations for the sp69 and sp76 devices were in some cases larger, which is particularly visible in the correlated color temperature. Deviations of about up to 15 K were considered normal, whereas clearly larger differences indicate weaknesses, especially in the LED peak region where small changes in color coordinates can lead to larger changes in CCT.

Table 15 Illuminance, chromaticity coordinates xyz and correlated color temperature (CCT) for the different sources calculated from the spectral irradiance measurements of the reference spectroradiometer.

	Illuminance	x	y	z	CCT
RGB	3765.4 lx	0.2434	0.2503	0.5063	–
NICHIA	325.2 lx	0.3698	0.3163	0.3139	3775 K
LIS-A	1589.8 lx	0.3848	0.3874	0.2278	3962 K
LIS-A ²	1898.4 lx	0.3379	0.3500	0.3121	5280 K

Table 16 Deviation of photometric and colorimetric quantities calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the RGB source.

Spectrometer	Illuminance	x	y	z
sp08	-0.6 %	0.0 %	-0.2 %	0.1 %
sp13	-2.0 %	-2.2 %	0.4 %	0.9 %
sp37	-2.1 %	-0.4 %	-0.6 %	0.5 %
sp38	-1.2 %	0.1 %	-0.5 %	0.2 %
sp49	0.3 %	-0.1 %	0.6 %	-0.2 %
sp61	-1.5 %	-2.2 %	0.1 %	1.0 %

sp69	-1.1 %	-4.4 %	1.2 %	1.5 %
sp76	0.2 %	0.2 %	1.6 %	-0.9 %
sp77	-0.5 %	0.1 %	0.2 %	-0.1 %

Table 17 Deviation of photometric and colorimetric quantities calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the NICHIA source.

Spectrometer	Illuminance	x	y	z	CCT
sp08	-0.2 %	-0.0 %	-0.1 %	0.2 %	1.0 K
sp13	-0.9 %	-0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	2.7 K
sp23	-0.3 %	-0.1 %	0.0 %	0.1 %	13.8 K
sp37	0.0 %	-0.2 %	-0.1 %	0.3 %	22.6 K
sp38	-0.3 %	0.1 %	0.1 %	-0.2 %	-9.3 K
sp49	0.3 %	-0.1 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	7.9 K
sp61	-0.0 %	0.0 %	0.1 %	-0.2 %	-0.1 K
sp69	-1.2 %	-0.4 %	-0.4 %	0.8 %	38.4 K
sp76	1.1 %	0.3 %	0.4 %	-0.7 %	-24.7 K
sp77	-0.3 %	0.1 %	0.0 %	-0.1 %	-6.7 K

Table 18 Deviation of photometric and colorimetric quantities calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the LIS-A source.

Spectrometer	Illuminance	x	y	z	CCT
sp08	-0.7 %	-0.0 %	-0.0 %	0.1 %	0.2 K
sp13	-2.0 %	0.2 %	0.1 %	-0.4 %	-12.7 K
sp23	-0.7 %	0.1 %	-0.0 %	-0.1 %	-8.2 K
sp37	-1.4 %	-0.2 %	-0.1 %	0.5 %	14.7 K
sp38	-0.9 %	0.0 %	0.1 %	-0.1 %	-1.9 K
sp49	-0.5 %	0.2 %	0.1 %	-0.4 %	-13.0 K
sp61	-1.0 %	0.1 %	0.1 %	-0.4 %	-8.5 K
sp69	-1.2 %	0.1 %	-0.1 %	0.0 %	-15.2 K
sp76	0.3 %	0.5 %	0.5 %	-1.7 %	-40.5 K
sp77	-0.5 %	-0.1 %	-0.1 %	0.2 %	3.0 K

Table 19 Deviation of photometric and colorimetric quantities calculated from the spectroradiometer measurements to the values of the reference spectroradiometer for the LIS-A² source.

Spectrometer	Illuminance	x	y	z	CCT
sp08	-0.4 %	-0.1 %	-0.1 %	0.2 %	7.4 K
sp13	-1.0 %	0.1 %	0.2 %	-0.3 %	-16.7 K
sp23	-0.2 %	-0.0 %	0.0 %	-0.0 %	2.4 K
sp37	-1.6 %	-0.2 %	-0.1 %	0.4 %	29.4 K
sp38	-0.8 %	0.0 %	0.1 %	-0.1 %	-4.5 K
sp49	-0.1 %	0.1 %	0.0 %	-0.1 %	-9.3 K
sp61	0.2 %	0.1 %	0.2 %	-0.4 %	-14.8 K
sp69	-0.9 %	-0.0 %	-0.1 %	0.2 %	2.7 K
sp76	0.3 %	0.6 %	0.6 %	-1.3 %	-78.9 K
sp77	-0.4 %	-0.0 %	-0.1 %	0.1 %	5.2 K

8. Solar spectral irradiance measurements

8.1. Nature and procedure of the measurement campaign

A measurement campaign in the frame of the NEWSTAND project was held from 20 to 27 April 2026 at PMOD/WRC. The campaign was aimed at testing the prototype sources developed in the NEWSTAND project on their applicability for calibrating spectroradiometers measuring spectral solar irradiance in the spectral range from 280 nm to 2150 nm.

8.2. Equipment and artefacts

8.2.1. Instruments for solar measurements

The following solar spectroradiometers operated by PMOD/WRC were used in the campaign:

QASUME

- Scanning double monochromator.
- Spectral range 250 nm to 550 nm.
- Spectral bandwidth (Full Width at Half Maximum): 0.8 nm.
- See Hülsen et al., 2016 for details [3].

QASUME-IR

- Scanning single monochromator
- Spectral range 550 nm to 1700 nm.
- Spectral bandwidth (FWHM): 1.5 nm (550 nm to 949 nm) and 2.5 nm from 950 nm to 1700 nm.
- See Gröbner et al., 2023 for details [4].

BTS-UV/VIS/NIR

- Array spectroradiometer, 2048 pixel.
- Spectral range 267 nm to 1050 nm.
- Spectral bandwidth (FWHM): 2.0 nm.
- See Gröbner et al., 2023 for details [4].

BTS-IR

- Array spectroradiometer, 512 pixel.
- Spectral range 944 nm to 2150 nm.
- Spectral bandwidth (FWHM): 8 nm.
- See Gröbner et al., 2023 for details [4].

The solar spectroradiometers were calibrated by PMOD/WRC prior and during the campaign using small-power tungsten-halogen lamps traceable to the spectral primary standard of PTB via transfer standard 1 kW FEL lamps [5].

8.2.2. Sources

The sources used during the campaign are described in a comparison report [7]. They were selected to cover as much as possible the spectral solar range measured with the solar spectroradiometers:

Table 20 List of sources used in the campaign.

Device name	Description	Institute
Aalto-UV	UV-phosphor LED source	Aalto
Nichia	LED standard lamp	NPL
LIS-A ² LED	multi LED transfer standard light sources, #1, #2, and #3	PTB
RISE-LED	NIR LED Source	RISE
XWS30	laser driven Xe-lamp	PTB
TuPS-II	tuneable portable monochromatic source with an apertured PQED detector	CMI

The sources were operated by the operators of the institutes that developed the sources. The spectral reference irradiances for the sources were supplied by the institutes.

PTB brought 2 BTS spectroradiometers (sp23, sp49) to provide stability checks of the PTB sources and also to provide a direct link to the measurements of the sources performed during the campaign held in October 2025 at PTB.

8.3. Results

8.3.1. Tunable portable source (TuPS-II)

The TuPS-II was operated by CMI at PMOD/WRC. The TuPS-II consists of a monochromatic source with a homogeneous output beam with a diameter of about 20 mm to cover the entrance optics of various detectors [6], Porrovecchio et al., 2026, in preparation]. During this campaign, an apertured PQED from CMI was used as reference detector. QASUME was used to measure the spectral output of the TuPS. Figure 32 shows the measurements performed with QASUME at several wavelength settings of the TuPS.

Figure 32 Spectral irradiance measurements of QASUME at several wavelength settings of the TuPS.

These measurements covered a bandwidth of ± 20 nm around the nominal output wavelength of TuPS. It was found that this spectral range is needed to measure all of the dispersed radiation from TuPS. Figure 33 shows the comparison between the irradiances measured by the PQED and the integrated irradiances from QASUME. The error bars represent the expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) of QASUME.

Figure 33 Ratio between the integrated irradiances from QASUME and the irradiances measured by the PQED.

As can be seen in the figure, the agreement is excellent, with differences between QASUME and the PQED of less than 1% across the whole sampled spectral range.

8.3.2. Aalto-UV

The UV source from Aalto was measured by PMOD/WRC (QASUME) during the campaign. Due to a malfunctioning of the source, it could not be measured by PTB during the campaign. The reference spectrum used for comparison was therefore the measurements by PTB during the campaign in October 2025. Figure 34 shows the measurements of the source by QASUME and PTB.

Figure 34 Measurements of Aalto-UV with QASUME and PTB. The top panel shows the irradiance spectrum on a linear scale, the middle panel the same irradiance on a log scale, and the bottom panel the ratio between the measurements of PMOD/WRC (QASUME) to PTB. The light grey area represents the combined relative expanded uncertainty.

As can be seen in the figure, the measurements by PMOD/WRC are lower than from PTB in October 2025. This could be due to changes of the source between the measurements done by PTB and those at PMOD/WRC.

8.3.3. RISE-LED

The source from RISE was measured by QASUME-IR and PTB. The spectral irradiance of the source was also provided by RISE. Figure 5 shows the measurements of the source at PMOD/WRC.

Figure 35 Measurements of RISE-LED with QASUME and PTB. The top panel shows the irradiance spectrum on a linear scale, the middle panel the same irradiance on a log scale, and the bottom panel the ratio between the measurements of PMOD/WRC (QASUME) to PTB (black curve) and between the RISE spectrum and PTB (blue curve). The light grey area represents the combined relative expanded uncertainty.

The measurements between PMOD/WRC and PTB agree quite well, with slight discrepancies at wavelengths shorter than 800 nm. The measurements agree within the combined expanded uncertainties of PMOD/WRC and PTB at wavelengths longer than 800 nm. However, the spectrum provided by RISE is about 20% higher than those measurements, indicating that the source might have changed during transport from RISE to PMOD/WRC.

8.3.4. XWS30

The source was measured by QASUME (250 nm to 550 nm) and QASUME-IR (550 nm to 1700 nm), and BTS (BTS-VIS and BTS-IR) from PMOD/WRC as shown in Figure 36. The measurements of the BTS were bandwidth corrected. The source was measured by PTB before and after the campaign and used as reference to calibrate the spectroradiometers of PMOD/WRC.

Figure 36 Measurements of XWS30 with QASUME and BTS from PMOD/WRC and from PTB. The top panel shows the irradiance spectrum on a linear scale, the middle panel the same irradiance on a log scale, and the bottom panel the ratio between the measurements to the reference spectrum from PTB spectrum. The light grey and blue areas represent the combined relative expanded uncertainty.

As can be seen in the figure the measurements all agree to within their combined expanded uncertainties at wavelengths longer than about 400 nm. Some deviations occur where the XWS30 spectrum shows strong spectral gradients.

8.3.5. LIS-A²

Three LIS-A² LED devices were operated at PMOD/WRC to calibrate the QASUME, QASUME-IR and BTS spectroradiometers. Figure 37 shows the measurements of LIS-A² LED#1.

Figure 37 Measurements of LIS-A² LED#1 with QASUME and BTS from PMOD/WRC and from PTB. The top panel shows the irradiance spectrum on a linear scale, the middle panel the same irradiance on a log scale, and the bottom panel the ratio between the measurements to the reference spectrum from PTB spectrum. The light grey and blue areas represent the combined relative expanded uncertainty.

As can be seen in the figure, the calibrations in the spectral interval between 340 nm and 1000 nm are very consistent and agree very well.

8.3.6. NICHIA

The NICHIA source was measured at PMOD/WRC using the QASUME and QASUME-IR spectroradiometers. The nominal distance was set to 500 mm, which led to very low signals, close to the sensitivity threshold of the QASUME-IR spectroradiometer. The reference spectrum was measured by PTB during the campaign. The spectrum from NPL is shown in the figure as well. Figure 38 shows the measurements of the NICHIA source.

Figure 38 Measurements of NICHIA with QASUME and QASUME-IR from PMOD/WRC and from NPL and PTB. The top panel shows the irradiance spectrum on a linear scale, the middle panel the same irradiance on a logscale, and the bottom panel the ratio between the measurements to the reference spectrum from PTB spectrum. The blue curve represents the ratio between the spectrum from NPL and PTB. The light grey and blue areas represent the combined relative expanded uncertainty.

8.4. Implications of the results for solar measurements

A figure showing the spectral coverage of the various sources and their intensity with respect to a solar spectra is shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39 Spectra of a solar spectrum (measured at Davos, 22 April 2026, 11:15 UTC) and of the sources measured during the campaign. The spectrum of a 1 kW FEL lamp is shown as blue curve.

As can be seen in the figure, most sources only cover a portion of the solar spectrum. The tungsten halogen 1 kW FEL lamp and the XWS30 source are the only sources whose spectra cover the whole solar spectrum. In the UV (250 nm to 400 nm), the Aalto-UV and XWS30 sources provide irradiances which are more

powerful than traditional tungsten-halogen sources, while at longer wavelengths their irradiance output decreases.

8.5. Conclusions

A preliminary conclusion from the study is that several sources developed within the project can be used to calibrate solar spectroradiometers, depending on the spectral range of interest. However, only the XWS30 source can be used when a calibration across the whole solar spectrum is required. Apart from the UV, all sources have significant lower irradiance output than the 1 kW FEL lamp, which could be problematic for calibrating solar spectroradiometers, which are optimized for much higher irradiance measurements.

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